

STEM Inclusion is an Important Step Towards the Future

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ABSTRACT

Inclusive education emphasizes the right of all children to learn, regardless of their disabilities, and promotes their participation in mainstream education programs. It recognizes the needs of all learners and creates conditions for their development, including individualized instruction and special services. Inclusion is seen as a process that responds to the diverse needs of students and promotes their active participation in the educational process and social life. The values and principles of inclusive education include the absolute recognition of all children's learning capabilities, teachers' cooperation with all students, continuous improvement of educational structures, and the rapid development of inclusion as part of an inclusive society. STEM is an innovative approach to learning that combines science, technology, engineering, and mathematics, providing students with the opportunity to acquire knowledge through practice and a deep understanding of processes.

Key words

inclusive education, educational needs, students, STEM.

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Інклюзія STEM – важливий поступ в майбутнє

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АНОТАЦІЯ

Інклюзивна освіта підкреслює право всіх дітей на навчання, незалежно від їхніх особливостей, та сприяє їх участі у загальноосвітніх програмах. Ця система визнає потреби всіх учнів і створює умови для їхнього розвитку, включаючи індивідуальне навчання та отримання спеціальних послуг. Інклюзія розглядається як процес, що відповідає на різноманітні потреби учнів та сприяє їхній активній участі в освітньому процесі та суспільному житті. Цінності і принципи інклюзивної освіти включають абсолютне визнання можливостей усіх дітей для навчання, співпрацю вчителів з усіма учнями, постійне вдосконалення освітніх структур та стрімкий розвиток інклюзії як частини інклюзивного суспільства. STEM – це інноваційний підхід до навчання, який поєднує науку, технології, інженерію та математику, забезпечуючи учням можливість здобувати знання на основі практики та глибокого розуміння процесів.

Ключові слова

інклюзивна освіта, освітні потреби, учні, STEM.

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Introduction / Вступ

Nowadays, every primary and secondary education institution teaches students with special educational needs, they study on equal terms with others, and usually do not receive the necessary attention. Usually, these students prefer the last class, avoiding excessive contact with teachers and classmates, and unfortunately, there are often cases when teachers support the policy of their students, minimizing contact in class.

Modern pedagogy emphasizes that everyone has the same right to receive any kind of education, and no one has the right to put obstacles in their way! Therefore, inclusion is not a sentence, nor is it a reason for distant communication with a child. A thorough understanding of this issue is the goal of everyone who has the honor of calling themselves a modern teacher.

Results / Результати

First of all, it should be noted that a teacher teaches to love and be able to learn, ignites the fire of knowledge in a student, no matter who he or she is, because as Konstantin Ushynsky poetically said: "A student is not a vessel to be filled, but a torch to be lit."

After analyzing the literature on the relevant topic (Clements et al., 2021; Moore et al, 2020; Jones, 2016), we have the opportunity to acquire specialized knowledge to achieve professionalism in the research material.

Inclusive education is a system of educational services based on the principle of ensuring the fundamental right of children to education and the right to receive it at the place of residence, which provides for the education of a child with special educational needs in a general education institution (Chernukha et al., 2021).

Inclusion is the process of increasing the degree of participation of all citizens in social life. It is a policy and process that enables all children to participate in all programs.

In particular, inclusion emphasizes the provision of opportunities for equal participation of children with disabilities (physical, social and emotional) in the general education system, for individual choice and for obtaining special services and accommodations for those who need them.

Inclusion is seen as a process of recognizing and responding to the diversity of needs of all learners. It involves their active participation in the process of acquiring knowledge, in cultural and social life. Inclusion leads to a reduction of segregation in the education system. It requires changes and modifications to the content, approaches, structure and strategy of education to meet the needs of all children, guided by the belief that general education systems have a responsibility to educate all children (Liubarets et al., 2021).

One of the main objectives of inclusion is to respond to a wide range of educational needs in the school environment and beyond.

Inclusive education, especially primary education, has its own values and principles, which include:

- 1) absolute recognition that all children, without exception, can learn;
- 2) the need for teachers to work fruitfully with all children, regardless of their age, nationality, language, origin, or developmental characteristics, but also taking into account the above factors
- 3) continuous improvement of educational structures, systems and methods to meet the developmental needs of all children;
- 4) rapid development of inclusion in education as part of a broader strategy to create an inclusive society;
- 5) creating and supporting this area as a dynamic process that is in constant development.

We see inclusion in education as one of the many aspects of inclusion in our society.

Inclusion involves adapting schools, their general educational philosophy and policies to the needs of all students, including those with special needs. Inclusion requires changes at all levels of education, as it is a special system of education that embraces the entire diverse student population

and differentiates the educational process to meet the needs of students of all groups and categories. This differentiation requires that each educational institution has both modern teachers with inclusion skills and methodological tools for their implementation, and the global technological revolution that has raised the level of society to a new “information” level comes to the rescue. It is the flexibility and diversity of the latest teaching methods and tools that give additional impetus to the development of inclusive primary and secondary schools. Such methods and tools are united under the acronym STEM, which is one of the important tools of the New Ukrainian School.

STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) is a term that refers to an approach to the educational process; according to which the basis for acquiring knowledge is a simple and accessible visualization of scientific phenomena, which “makes it easy to capture and acquire knowledge based on practice and a deep understanding of processes.”

The acronym STEM was coined in 2001 to denote a trend in the educational and professional spheres by researchers at the US National Science Foundation.

Thus, during a STEM lesson, it is possible to improve knowledge and skills in several subjects at once, including labor training, biology, physics, and mathematics.

An interesting tool for STEM and the New Ukrainian School is the use of the LEGO construction set. To this end, the international Six Bricks program was introduced into the educational process.

If you look at the structure of even the simplest STEM lessons that do not require a laboratory equipped with technology, you will see that they are ideal and develop abilities for students with special educational needs and children with different health conditions.

STEM education is a category that defines the appropriate pedagogical process (technology) for the formation and development of mental, cognitive and creative qualities of young people that contribute to professional competitiveness in the modern labor market. STEM education is carried out through an interdisciplinary approach to building curricula of educational institutions of different levels, and is especially important for people with special educational needs. The mission of STEM approaches is to expand educational opportunities and help socialize young people with different health conditions.

The essence of STEM education is not based on mastery of theory, but on the ability to use one’s knowledge in practice.

The crucial importance of STEM education in working with students with special educational needs. In particular, STEM education provides special children with accessibility, diversity and dynamism of learning, teamwork, the ability to apply the knowledge gained in real life, the development of critical thinking, confidence in their own abilities, and a direct path from education to career.

STEM classes are based on solving real-world problems. In addition, at each stage of the lesson, students solve a specific problem or perform a specific task with clear conditions and expectations for the result. This is easier for most students with special educational needs than working with abstract concepts.

Engage students with special educational needs in STEM activities based on their strengths and interests.

To do this, clearly define the purpose of the task in general and each of the stages. Set the level at which your students with special educational needs should complete the task. Provide correct and prompt feedback so that students can adjust their actions as needed.

Many tasks involve working with a variety of tools, from scissors and modeling knives to drills, soldering irons, and more. Be there for the students as they work with these tools, but at the same time, let them do the work, guiding and supporting them whenever possible. This will help them gain more independence and confidence in their own abilities.

Children are constantly changing the format of work and the form of activity, and it is possible to choose the most comfortable format of work or alternate them.

Conclusions / Висновки

To summarize the material, we can say the following: by teaching children with special needs using STEM education tools, we will have inclusive students, fully active citizens, and good

specialists in modern professions in the future. It will be much easier for children to find both inspiration for learning and their vocation in life.

References

- Chernukha, N., Petrova, M., Vasyliieva-Khalatnykova, M., Krupnyk, Z., & Krasilova, Y. (2021). The role of the sociocultural environment of inclusion in the modern educational institution. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 10(3), 211–222. <http://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v10n3p211>
- Clements, D. H., Vinh, M., Lim, C. I., & Sarama, J. (2021). STEM for Inclusive Excellence and Equity. *Early Education and Development*, 32(1), 148–171. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10409289.2020.1755776>
- Jones, S. (2016). More than an intervention: Strategies for increasing diversity and inclusion in STEM. *Journal for Multicultural Education*, 10(2), 234–246. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JME-12-2015-0046>
- Liubarets, V., & Vasyliieva, H. (2021). Educational workers methodological competence formation in the conditions of inclusive learning. *Paradigm of Knowledge*, 1(45). [https://doi.org/10.26886/2520-7474.1\(45\)2021.11](https://doi.org/10.26886/2520-7474.1(45)2021.11)
- Moore, M. E., Vega, D. M., Wiens, K. M., & Caporale, N. (2020). Connecting theory to practice: Using self-determination theory to better understand inclusion in STEM. *Journal of Microbiology & Biology Education*, 21(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jmbe.v21i1.1955>